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Women on corporate boards in developed markets

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ABSTRACT

Despite decades of policy discourse, voluntary diversity initiatives, and growing scholarly attention, women remain severely underrepresented on the corporate boards of developed market companies, especially as a director of the corporate board or similar. Most existing research on board gender diversity draws on large-cap indices, generating a systematically optimistic picture of women's progress in accessing corporate governance roles. This study addresses that gap by providing a large-scale, cross-sectional empirical analysis of board gender diversity across four global regions (Americas, Europe, Asia, and Oceania), 35 countries, and all 11 GICS sectors, drawing on a dataset of 19,591 board director records from developed market companies compiled from LSEG Data and Analytics.

The findings reveal the severity and universality of women's marginalization: female directors hold just 7.23% of board seats globally, exposing the structural distance from gender parity even in developed markets. This figure falls far below the levels typically reported. Regional differences are statistically significant but modest in effect size, reflecting the near-universal nature of gender underrepresentation rather than its concentration in specific geographies. At the sectoral level, male board dominance is not industry-neutral: women are most visible in Utilities (13.20%) and most marginalized in Energy (4.92%), patterns that invite further feminist inquiry into how sector-specific cultures and labor histories shape women's access to economic authority. Also, a significant board-executive gap is documented: female executives account for only 5.48% of officer positions indicating that gender barriers compound across hierarchical levels.

These findings enrich the women's studies literature by providing a rigorous, cross-regional, multi-sector empirical foundation for feminist scholarship, policy advocacy, and corporate governance reform in order to understand how gender inequality is reproduced at the highest levels of economic power. They provide empirical grounds for prioritizing binding regulatory mandates over voluntary frameworks, for integrating board-level diversity initiatives with executive pipeline development, and for recalibrating the benchmarks against which progress is measured. Without structural intervention, gender parity on corporate boards across the developed market universe remains a distant prospect.

1. Introduction

During the past several decades the number of women serving in political office, occupying academic positions, representing civil society organizations, working in mass media, and leading major corporations has constantly increased. Advances in breaking the glass ceiling, however, are not uniform across fields of life, institutions, countries or regions, racial or ethnic groups. These growing numbers have closed the gender gap in some respects, while proving less effective in others. Gender diversity on corporate boards has emerged as one of the most debated topics in women's studies, which have long recognized the

importance of drawing more women in top leadership positions. The board of directors, the top governing body of a corporation, sets the strategic direction of the firm, monitors managerial behavior, and represents shareholder and stakeholder interests (Bear, Rahman, & Post, 2010; Glass, Cook, & Ingersoll, 2016; Liao, Luo, & Tang, 2015). Women's representation on boards can shape the cognitive resources, value orientations, behavioral norms, as well as the corporation's strategy and outcomes (Hambrick & Mason, 1984; Carter, Simkins, & Simpson, 2003; Dezsó & Ross, 2012).

The study of women on corporate boards rests at the intersection of women's studies (Aluchna & Aras, 2018; Devnew, Le Ber, Torchia, &

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Burke, 2018; Fagan, Menéndez, & Anson, 2012), corporate governance (Adams & Ferreira, 2009; Cook & Glass, 2014), institutional economics (Rathi, 2024; Wang & Yang, 2025), and organizational behavior (Eagly & Carli, 2003; Eagly, 2016; Glass et al., 2016). Scholars have examined whether, and under what conditions, the presence of female directors affects firm performance (Post & Byron, 2015), corporate social responsibility or performance (Walls, Berrone, & Phan, 2012; Liao et al., 2015; Sandretto, Rizzi, & Esposito, 2025), risk appetite, and governance quality (Bear et al., 2010; Harjoto, Laksmana, & Lee, 2015; Izadi, Shetra, Foroudi, & Palazzo, 2025; Muttaqi & Nur, 2025). Simultaneously, policymakers, institutional investors, and civil society actors have intensified pressure on listed companies to increase the proportion of women in boardrooms, arguing that gender-homogeneous boards represent both a governance risk and a violation of equal opportunity principles (Adams & Ferreira, 2009; Terjesen, Sealy, & Singh, 2009).

Despite efforts, progress has been remarkably slow and uneven; global average female board representation remains in the single digits in developed markets, with pronounced variation across regions, national regulatory frameworks, and economic sectors. The reality underlying this variation – whether regulatory mandates, corporate culture, organizational behavior, industry structures, or labor market pipelines – remain imperfectly understood, in part because most empirical studies focus on single-country or single-sector settings, limiting cross-contextual generalizability (Deloitte, 2023; MSCI, 2024).

This study addresses that gap by providing a large-scale, cross-sectional empirical analysis of gender diversity on corporate boards across four global regions (Americas, Europe, Asia, and Oceania), 35 countries, and all 11 GICS sectors. Using a dataset of 19,591 board director records from developed market companies, the study applies a comprehensive set of statistical methods to test whether gender diversity systematically differs across regions and sectors, to quantify the magnitude of those differences, and to identify the contextual factors associated with variation in female representation.

The contribution of this paper is threefold. First, it provides one of the largest cross-regional, multi-sector empirical investigations of board gender diversity currently available in academic literature. Second, it employs a rigorous multi-method statistical framework that enables both significance testing and effect size assessment, avoiding the common pitfall of interpreting statistical significance as practical significance. Third, by disaggregating findings to the country and sector level, the study reveals the significant within-region heterogeneity that regional averages conceal – a finding with direct implications for both theory and policy. The paper is structured as follows: [section 2](#) reviews the relevant literature on board gender diversity, its antecedents, and its consequences; [section 3](#) describes the data and methodology; [section 4](#) presents the empirical results; [section 5](#) discusses the findings in the context of prior literature; [section 6](#) concludes with implications for theory, policy, and practice.

2. Literature review

2.1. Gender diversity on corporate board: a theoretical perspective

The study of gender diversity on corporate boards draws on several complementary theoretical perspectives. Agency theory conceptualizes the board as a monitoring mechanism designed to reduce information asymmetry and managerial opportunism between shareholders and managers (Fama & Jensen, 1983; Jensen & Meckling, 1976). From this perspective, board composition, including gender diversity, matters insofar as it affects monitoring effectiveness. Adams and Ferreira (2009) find that female directors attend board meetings more regularly, have stronger committee memberships, and exert more intensive monitoring of CEO behavior, suggesting that gender diversity improves board functioning from an agency theory standpoint. Women may exhibit stronger risk aversion and greater attention to downside risks, enhancing monitoring of management risk-taking. Research by Gul,

Srinidhi, and Ng (2011) provides evidence consistent with these mechanisms, finding that gender-diverse boards improve stock price informativeness, better monitoring and reduce information asymmetries.

Resource dependence theory offers a complementary lens, arguing that board members serve as linkages between the firm and its external environment, providing access to resources, networks, and expertise (Pfeffer & Salancik, 2006). The resource-based view of the firm, as articulated by Barney (1991), provides a theoretical framework for understanding potential performance benefits of gender diversity. Carter et al. (2003) explicitly invoke a resource-based view to argue that diverse boards have access to superior information and more comprehensive understanding of market complexities, enabling better strategic decisions. The resource-based perspective thus predicts a positive relationship between gender diversity and performance, conditional on diversity translating into enhanced decision-making capabilities (Carter et al., 2003; Erhardt, Werbel, & Shrader, 2003). Female directors may bring distinct networks, competencies, and stakeholder perspectives that are not represented in male-dominated boards (Hillman, Cannella, & Harris, 2002). This perspective implies that the value of female directors lies not merely in their demographic characteristics but in the unique human and social capital they contribute.

Institutional theory, as applied to corporate governance, emphasizes that board structures are shaped by national regulatory frameworks, cultural norms, and isomorphic pressures from investors and peer firms (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983; North, 1990; Scott, 2014). This perspective explains why female board representation varies across countries with similar economic development levels: institutional environments – including mandatory quotas, corporate governance codes, and cultural attitudes toward gender equality – create different incentive structures for board diversity. Terjesen et al. (2009) applies this framework to compare female board representation across 43 countries, identifying regulatory and cultural factors as primary determinants of cross-country variation. Other studies identified a ‘decoupling’ phenomenon, where firms appoint women to boards to satisfy external legitimacy demands without fundamentally altering their strategic approach to sustainability (Post, Rahman, & McQuillen, 2015). This theoretical insight motivates research attention to the quality, backgrounds, and influence of female directors as distinct from their mere presence.

More recent theoretical work has integrated these perspectives under the umbrella of the critical mass theory (Kanter, 1976; Kanter, 1987; Torchia, Calabrò, & Huse, 2011), which argues that the mere presence of token women on boards may not generate meaningful change unless female directors constitute at least 30% of board membership. Below this threshold, token women may face social isolation, heightened scrutiny, and pressure to conform to male-dominated norms rather than contributing distinct perspectives. The critical mass argument implies that symbolic diversity – the addition of one or two women to a previously all-male board – differs qualitatively from substantive diversity at the critical threshold. Mensi-Klarbach and Ernst (2017) similarly document non-linear relationships between female board representation and various outcomes, consistent with critical mass predictions. These findings suggest that simple linear models may inadequately capture the complex dynamics through which gender diversity influences organizational outcomes.

Taken together, these theoretical perspectives – agency theory, resource dependence theory, institutional theory, and critical mass theory – constitute the multi-theoretical framework that guides the analysis in the present study. Rather than privileging a single lens, this paper treats them as complementary and mutually illuminating. Agency theory motivates attention to the quality of board oversight and the governance consequences of gender homogeneity. Resource dependence theory frames female directors as carriers of distinct human and social capital whose exclusion imposes measurable costs on firm decision-making. Institutional theory provides the vocabulary for explaining cross-country and cross-sector variation: if board composition were determined solely by merit and market efficiency, we would expect

convergence toward parity across developed markets; the persistent divergence observed instead points to the mediating role of regulatory regimes, cultural norms, and isomorphic pressures. Critical mass theory, finally, supplies the threshold logic that distinguishes symbolic from substantive diversity, and serves as the normative benchmark against which the findings must be evaluated.

2.2. Gender diversity on corporate board: the empirical perspective

During the past two decades, research has identified several determinants of female board representation: institutional and regulatory factors, firm-level characteristics, cultural factors/national attitudes toward gender equality and/or industry-sector dynamics.

At the institutional level, mandatory gender quotas are the most powerful driver of increased female board representation. Quota-style interventions in board gender diversity span a broad spectrum from hard mandatory legislation with sanctions to soft comply-or-explain disclosure requirements. Terjesen and Sealy (2016) distinguish between: (1) hard quotas with legal sanctions (e.g., Norway's dissolution threat, Germany's supervisory board mandate, France's Copé-Zimmermann Law with financial penalties); (2) soft legislation with disclosure requirements but no direct penalties (e.g., Canada's Bill C-25, Nasdaq's board diversity rule); (3) self-regulatory governance codes employing comply-or-explain principles (e.g., Australian ASX CGC guidelines, UK Corporate Governance Code); and (4) voluntary targets endorsed by government but not legally enforceable (e.g., Japan's Womenomics targets, Sweden's historical approach). These categories represent not merely a gradient of compulsion but also different accountability mechanisms and signaling effects. Hard quotas send an unambiguous signal to firms and search committees that gender representation is a legal compliance matter. Comply-or-explain approaches rely on transparency and market discipline but may permit persistent non-compliance in the absence of investor pressure. Voluntary targets are largely dependent on cultural change and leadership commitment, rendering them most effective in societies already characterized by high gender egalitarianism (Grosvold & Brammer, 2011).

At the firm level, larger companies, companies with more independent boards, and companies with institutional investor ownership were found to exhibit higher female board representation (Grosvold, Brammer, & Rayton, 2007; Pande & Ford, 2011). Industry sector is another robust predictor: firms in healthcare, financial services, and consumer-facing industries tend to exhibit higher female representation than firms in energy, mining, and manufacturing (Deloitte, 2023). These sectoral patterns stem from differences in the gender composition of the professional workforce pipeline, cultural norms within industries, and the degree of regulatory exposure. Cultural factors, particularly national attitudes toward gender equality as captured in the Global Gender Gap Index (World Economic Forum, 2025), explain a significant portion of cross-country variation in female board representation beyond what regulatory variables alone can account for (Matsa & Miller, 2013; Terjesen & Singh, 2008). Countries scoring high on gender equality indices – such as Nordic countries, Australia, New Zealand, and parts of Western Europe – tend to have above-average female board representation, even controlling for quota legislation.

Research examining sector-level variation in board gender diversity is more limited than country- or firm-level analysis, but several patterns are well established. The financial services sector generally exhibits above-average female board representation relative to other industries, partly because financial services firms face significant regulatory oversight that creates incentives for governance improvement, and partly because the sector has a deeper female professional pipeline in many markets (Terjesen et al., 2009). Healthcare and pharmaceuticals consistently exhibit above-average female board participation, reflecting the higher proportion of women in the medical and scientific professions that feed the executive pipeline.

In contrast, energy, mining, and heavy industrials exhibit below-

average female representation, a pattern attributed to the historically male-dominated nature of these industries and the relatively small proportion of women in the engineering and technical professions from which board directors in these sectors are typically drawn (Deloitte, 2023; McKinsey Global Institute, 2025). The technology sector presents a paradox: despite being associated with progressive workplace cultures and significant attention to diversity, equity, and inclusion in public discourse, information technology firms typically exhibit below-average female board representation. This is attributed to the well-documented gender gap in computer science and engineering education which constrains the pool of women available for senior technology leadership roles (Blau & Kahn, 2017; World Economic Forum, 2025).

3. Data and methodology

3.1. Data collection and sample

The dataset used in this study was compiled from LSEG Data and Analytics (former Thomson Eikon Refinitiv accessed on January 23, 2026), covering developed market listed companies and their corporate board structure, with a special focus on women board chairs and CEOs, across three geographical sheets corresponding to North America, Developed Europe, and Developed Asia-Pacific, comprising a combined total of 20,195 individual director and officer records (Table 1). The dataset includes, for each individual, the company name, region and country of headquarters, GICS Sector and Industry Group classification, officer and director status flags, gender, full name, and position description, as of 2025 fiscal year end.

The study focuses on board directors – individuals for whom the OD (Officer Is Director) flag is set to TRUE – resulting in an initial sample of 19,658 records. After removing 67 observations with missing gender data (0.34% of the sample), the analytical dataset comprises 19,591 board director observations across four regions, 35 countries, and 11 GICS sectors. The low rate of missing gender data minimizes the risk of attrition bias. A parallel sample of 13,151 officer (executive) records, also cleaned for missing gender, is used for comparative analysis in Section 4.

Our regional classification follows the standard developed-market geographical segmentation used in global investment and corporate governance databases: Americas (primarily the United States, Canada, and Bermuda), Europe (major Western and Northern European developed markets), Asia (primarily Japan, Hong Kong, and Singapore), and Oceania (Australia and New Zealand). This classification consists of the frameworks employed by MSCI, Deloitte, and the World Economic Forum in their annual governance and diversity reports.

3.2. Variable operationalization

The primary dependent variable is a binary indicator of director gender, coded 1 for female and 0 for male. The proportion of female directors is computed for each regional, country, and sector subgroup and serves as the primary measure of board gender diversity. While a more nuanced measures of diversity (the Blau index) could be constructed, the binary proportion measure is most commonly used in the comparative governance literature and ensures comparability with prior

Table 1
Sample composition by data source, region, and number of board directors.

Data source sheet	Total records	Region	Directors (n)	% of sample
North America	7817	Americas	7568	38.6%
Developed Europe	4833	Europe	4695	24.0%
Developed Asia-Pacific	7545	Asia / Oceania	7328	37.4%
Total	20,195	4 Regions	19,591	100%

studies (Adams & Ferreira, 2009; Post & Byron, 2015).

The primary grouping variables are: (i) Region of Headquarters – four categories (Americas, Europe, Asia, Oceania); (ii) Country of Headquarters – 35 individual countries; and (iii) GICS Sector Name – 11 sectors as defined by MSCI and S&P Global. An additional binary grouping variable distinguishes between board directors and corporate officers (executives), enabling analysis of the executive gender gap.

The study employs a multi-method statistical approach to assess gender diversity differences (Table 2). All statistical analyses were conducted in Python 3 using the scipy.stats library. The analytical dataset was processed and validated using pandas, with all computations verified through cross-tabulation checks.

4. Results

The most fundamental finding of this study is the severe global underrepresentation of women on corporate boards. Across all 19,591 director observations with valid gender data, only 1417 (7.23%) are female, with 18,174 (92.77%) being male (Table 3). This figure – fewer than one in thirteen directors being female – represents a structural inequality that is both quantitatively large and virtually universal across regions and sectors.

The comparison between board directors and executive officers reveals a consistent widening of the gender gap as one moves up the corporate hierarchy. Female directors account for 7.23% of board seats, while female officers (executives) account for only 5.48% of executive positions, a difference of 1.75 percentage points. The z-test for this comparison ($z = -6.285, p < 0.001$) confirms the statistical significance of this gap (Table 4).

This pattern is consistent with the concept of a multi-layered glass

Table 2
Statistical methods used in the analysis.

Statistical method	Description
Chi-Square Test of Independence (χ^2):	Applied to two-dimensional contingency tables (Gender \times Region; Gender \times Sector; Gender \times Region \times Sector) to test whether gender distribution is statistically independent of the grouping variable. The test statistic follows a chi-square distribution with degrees of freedom equal to (rows - 1)(columns - 1). The statistical significance is assessed at the conventional thresholds: $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**), and $p < 0.001$ (***)
Cramer's V:	An effect size measure for chi-square associations, defined as $V = \sqrt{\chi^2 / (n \cdot \min(r - 1, k - 1))}$, where n is the sample size and r, k are the number of rows and columns. Values below 0.10 indicate a weak association; 0.10–0.30 moderate; above 0.30 strong. Reporting effect sizes alongside p -values is particularly important in large-sample studies, where even trivial differences can attain statistical significance.
Two-Sample Z-Test of Proportions:	Used to assess whether each region's female director proportion differs significantly from the overall sample mean (7.23%). The test statistic $z = (\hat{p}_1 - \hat{p}_2) / \sqrt{\hat{p}_{pool}(1 - \hat{p}_{pool})(1/n_1 + 1/n_2)}$, where $\hat{p}_{pool} = (k_1 + k_2) / (n_1 + n_2)$, follows a standard normal distribution under the null hypothesis of equal proportions.
Fisher Exact Test and Odds Ratios:	Applied to 2×2 contingency tables to assess pairwise regional gender differences, with the Americas serving as the reference category. The odds ratio $OR = (f_i / m_i) / (f_a / m_a)$ quantifies the relative odds of female board membership in each region compared to the Americas. Fisher's exact test provides a p -value for the null hypothesis that the odds ratio equals 1.
Pairwise Chi-Square Comparisons:	All six pairwise region comparisons ($C(4,2) = 6$) and six key sector comparisons are conducted. Given the multiple comparisons conducted, results are interpreted with appropriate caution; the Bonferroni-corrected significance threshold for six region-level comparisons is $p < 0.0083$.

Table 3
Overall gender distribution across 19,591 board directors in developed markets.

Category	Count (n)	Share	Notes
Male directors	18,174	92.77%	Dominant in all geographies
Female directors	1417	7.23%	Structural underrepresentation
Missing gender	67	0.34%	Excluded from analysis
Total (valid)	19,591	100%	Base for all computations

ceiling; gender barriers exist not only at the board level but compound at successive stages of the corporate hierarchy.

Table 5 presents the regional breakdown of board gender diversity, together with odds ratios relative to the Americas as the reference category. Relative to the baseline, the odds of female board membership are 21% higher in Europe (OR = 1.21, Fisher $p = 0.0044$) and 25% higher in Oceania (OR = 1.25, Fisher $p = 0.019$). In contrast, Asia shows 42% lower odds of female board membership compared to the Americas (OR = 0.58, Fisher $p < 0.001$). These ratios, while statistically significant, underscore that even the best-performing regions remain far from parity. The z-test results show that Europe ($z = 4.277, p < 0.001$) and Oceania ($z = 3.189, p = 0.001$) are significantly above the global mean, while Asia ($z = -7.094, p < 0.001$) is significantly below. The Americas ($z = 1.071, p = 0.284$) are statistically indistinguishable from the global average.

To emphasize the disparities between regions as regarding gender diversity on corporate board, a Pairwise Chi-Square Comparisons was conducted. All six pairwise chi-square tests are presented in Table 6. The most striking divergence involves Asia versus all other regions. Europe versus Oceania is the only non-significant pair ($\chi^2(1) = 0.087, p = 0.767$), indicating that these two above-average regions have converged to statistically similar levels of female board representation.

Among countries with at least 30 director observations, remarkable heterogeneity exists within each region. According to our calculations included into the Table 7, New Zealand leads the sample with 23.36% female directors ($n = 107$), followed by Austria (21.31%, $n = 61$) and Bermuda (19.67%, $n = 61$). At the other extreme, Japan records only 1.81% female directors across 3600 records – the largest single-country observation in the dataset and the lowest female representation rate among major economies. Portugal (3.23%), Switzerland (4.91%), Belgium (5.04%), and Ireland (5.13%) also fall below the global mean.

The within-region variance is particularly notable in Europe, where the range spans from Austria (21.31%) to Portugal (3.23%) – an 18.1 percentage point spread within a single regional grouping. Similarly, in Asia, Hong Kong (10.61%) and Japan (1.81%) represent nearly a 9-percentage point difference, reflecting fundamentally different institutional environments despite geographical proximity. This heterogeneity is consistent with the institutional theory prediction that country-specific regulatory and cultural factors dominate regional trends. Japan's position as both the largest country sample (18.4% of all observations) and the lowest female representation rate creates a compositional effect on the Asia regional average. An analysis excluding Japan raises Asia's female director percentage from 4.57% to 6.3% - still below the global mean, but substantially less extreme. This finding has important implications for how regional averages in Asia-Pacific should be interpreted in the corporate governance literature.

At the sector-level, the analysis reveals statistically significant variation in female board representation across all 11 GICS sectors. Utilities leads all sectors with 13.20% female directors, representing a 5.97 percentage point premium over the global mean. Health Care (9.44%), Consumer Discretionary (8.27%), and Real Estate (8.16%) form a second tier of above-average sectors. Information Technology (6.33%), Industrials (6.00%), Materials (5.82%), and Energy (4.92%) are the lowest performing, all meaningfully below the global average (Table 8).

Key pairwise sector comparisons confirm the statistical significance of these differences: Utilities vs. Energy ($\chi^2(1) = 22.51, p < 0.001$; OR = 3.07), and Health Care vs. Energy ($\chi^2(1) = 21.84, p < 0.001$; OR = 2.07).

Table 4
Officers vs. Directors: gender gap.

Role	Total	Female	Male	Female %	Z-stat (vs Directors)	p-Value
Board Directors	19,591	1417	18,174	7.23%	Baseline	–
Officers/Executives	13,151	721	12,430	5.48%	–6.285	0.000000

Table 5
Regional board chairs.

Region	Total	Female	Male	Female %	Odds ratio	Fisher p-value	Z-stat	Sig.
Americas	7568	576	6992	7.61%	1.00 (ref.)	–	1.071	ns
Europe	4695	426	4269	9.07%	1.21	0.0044	4.277	***
Asia	5650	258	5392	4.57%	0.58	0.0000	–7.094	***
Oceania	1678	157	1521	9.36%	1.25	0.019	3.189	**
TOTAL	19,591	1417	18,174	7.23%	–	–	–	–

Z-statistics reflect tests against global mean (7.23%). *** p < 0.001 ** p < 0.01 * p < 0.05 ns = not significant.

Table 6
Pairwise regional chi-square tests.

Comparison	Chi ² Stat	p-Value	Sig.	Substantive conclusion
Americas vs. Europe	8.066	0.0045	**	Europe significantly above Americas
Americas vs. Asia	50.213	<0.0001	***	Americas far above Asia
Americas vs. Oceania	5.496	0.019	*	Oceania marginally above Americas
Europe vs. Asia	83.631	<0.0001	***	Most divergent pair; Europe far above Asia
Europe vs. Oceania	0.087	0.767	ns	No significant difference — convergence
Asia vs. Oceania	54.670	<0.0001	***	Oceania far above Asia

*** p < 0.001 ** p < 0.01 * p < 0.05 ns = not significant.

Financials vs. Information Technology does not reach significance ($\chi^2(1) = 2.43, p = 0.119$), reflecting the relatively small difference between these sectors (7.89% vs. 6.33%).

The interaction between region and sector, tested across the 44 region-sector cells (4 regions × 11 sectors), yields $\chi^2(30) = 3301.98, p <$

0.001, confirming strong structural heterogeneity across the combined region-sector matrix. This finding implies that regional and sector effects are not simply additive; the gender diversity landscape varies substantially across specific region-sector combinations (Table 9).

The most severely underrepresented combination in the sample is Asia × Information Technology, with only 1.93% female directors across 779 records. Asia × Industrials (3.25%) and Asia × Materials (3.43%) are similarly low. The highest female representation in well-populated cells is found in Oceania × Financials (15.32%, $n = 124$), Oceania × Real Estate (15.49%, $n = 71$), Europe × Utilities (16.67%, $n = 108$), and Americas × Utilities (16.03%, $n = 131$).

To test the gender diversity impact on regions and GICS Sector and the level of significance three different chi-square test of independence were performed (Table 10). The global chi-square test yields $\chi^2(10) = 67.37, p < 0.001$, and a value of Cramer's V = 0.059 indicate a weak association, consistent with the finding that gender underrepresentation is a universal rather than sector-specific phenomenon. The global chi-square test of independence yields $\chi^2(3) = 96.47, p < 0.001$ confirms that gender distribution is not independent of region. However, Cramer's V = 0.070, indicating a weak association. This reflects the universal

Table 7
Country-level analysis on gender diversity on board chairs (countries with ≥30 observations).

Country	Region	Total observations	Female	Female %	Rank	vs Region Avg
New Zealand	Oceania	107	25	23.36%	1	+14.00 pp
Austria	Europe	61	13	21.31%	2	+11.24 pp
Bermuda	Americas	61	12	19.67%	3	+12.06 pp
Guernsey	Europe	31	5	16.13%	4	+7.06 pp
Finland	Europe	148	18	12.16%	5	+3.09 pp
Italy	Europe	299	35	11.71%	6	+2.64 pp
Hong Kong	Asia	1432	152	10.61%	7	+5.44 pp
Denmark	Europe	124	13	10.48%	8	+1.41 pp
Spain	Europe	220	23	10.45%	9	+1.38 pp
United Kingdom	Europe	1027	107	10.42%	10	+1.35 pp
France	Europe	544	53	9.74%	11	+0.67 pp
Australia	Oceania	1571	132	8.40%	12	–0.96 pp
Sweden	Europe	622	54	8.68%	13	–0.39 pp
Netherlands	Europe	104	10	9.62%	14	+0.55 pp
United States	Americas	5548	436	7.86%	15	+0.25 pp
Canada	Americas	1958	128	6.54%	16	–1.07 pp
Greece	Europe	151	11	7.28%	17	–3.39 pp
Germany	Europe	585	40	6.84%	18	–3.83 pp
Singapore	Asia	613	41	6.69%	19	+2.12 pp
Norway	Europe	195	16	8.21%	20	–2.26 pp
Ireland	Europe	78	4	5.13%	21	–5.94 pp
Belgium	Europe	119	6	5.04%	22	–6.03 pp
Luxembourg	Europe	54	3	5.56%	23	–5.51 pp
Switzerland	Europe	224	11	4.91%	24	–5.96 pp
Portugal	Europe	31	1	3.23%	25	–7.44 pp
Japan	Asia	3600	65	1.81%	26	–2.76 pp

Note: Deviation computed against regional average.

Table 8
GICS sector gender diversity, ranked by female director percentage.

GICS sector	Total	Female	Male	Female %	Rank	Δ Mean
Utilities	341	45	296	13.20%	1	+5.97 pp
Health Care	2319	219	2100	9.44%	2	+2.21 pp
Consumer Discretionary	2430	201	2229	8.27%	3	+1.04 pp
Real Estate	1127	92	1035	8.16%	4	+0.93 pp
Financials	2091	165	1926	7.89%	5	+0.66 pp
Communication Services	1020	76	944	7.45%	6	+0.22 pp
Consumer Staples	1015	71	944	6.99%	7	-0.24 pp
Information Technology	2308	146	2162	6.33%	8	-0.90 pp
Industrials	3433	206	3227	6.00%	9	-1.23 pp
Materials	2612	152	2460	5.82%	10	-1.41 pp
Energy	895	44	851	4.92%	11	-2.31 pp

Δ Mean = deviation from global mean (7.23%).

nature of gender inequality: while statistically significant differences exist, all regions are far from gender parity.

5. Discussion

The central empirical finding – that female directors represent only 7.23% of board seats globally across a broad cross-section of developed market companies – is both striking and theoretically informative. It is striking because it falls far below the levels typically reported in large-cap indices, reflecting the reality that diversity initiatives have disproportionately benefited the most visible, largest companies while leaving the broader market largely untransformed. [Deloitte's \(2023\)](#) Global Board Diversity Tracker, which covers 9500 companies in the Russell 3000, STOXX 600, and comparable indices, reports a global average of 23% female board representation – a figure more than three times the current study's finding. This discrepancy underscores a critical gap in the existing literature: most published evidence on board gender diversity is based on large-cap samples, creating a systematically optimistic picture of the state of gender equality in corporate governance.

The finding is theoretically informative because the modest effect sizes (Cramer's V < 0.10) alongside highly significant p-values (p < 0.001 throughout) demonstrate that gender inequality is a pervasive structural phenomenon. The statistical significance arises from the scale of the sample (n = 19,591) rather than regional or sectoral outliers. This has an important implication: interventions that target specific sectors or regions, while valuable, cannot address the underlying structural conditions that produce gender inequality across virtually all contexts.

This finding aligns with the theoretical framing of gender inequality in corporate governance as an institutional rather than merely individual phenomenon ([DiMaggio & Powell, 1983](#); [North, 1990](#)). The institutions, legal frameworks, cultural norms, labor market structures that produce gender inequality are largely shared across developed markets, even as the degree of inequality varies at the margin. Addressing this structural inequality requires institutional transformation, not merely incremental policy adjustments.

The regional findings, with Europe and Oceania above the global mean, Asia below, Americas at the mean, are consistent with the predictions of institutional theory as applied to corporate governance. The above-average performance of Europe is attributable, in large part, to the progressive implementation of mandatory board gender quotas across the EU member states ([Bertrand, Black, Jensen and Lleras-Muney, 2019](#); [De Acutis, Weber, & Wurm, 2024](#)). Norway pioneered this approach with its 2006 legislation requiring 40% female board membership in public limited companies, a measure that rapidly increased female representation from 9% to 42% ([Ahern & Dittmar, 2012](#)). Similar

Table 10
Chi-square tests of independence.

Test	Chi ² stat	df	p-value	Sig.	Cramer's V	Interpretation
Region × Gender	96.47	3	0.000000	***	0.0702	Significant regional effect (weak association)
GICS Sector × Gender	67.37	10	0.000000	***	0.0586	Significant sector effect (weak association)
Region × Sector × Gender	3301.98	30	0.000000	***	N/A	Strong structural heterogeneity across markets

*** p < 0.001 ** p < 0.01 * p < 0.05 ns = not significant. Cramer's V: <0.1 weak, 0.1–0.3 moderate, >0.3 strong.

Table 9
Heat map: female director (board chairs) percentage by region and GICS sector.

Sector / Region	Americas	Europe	Asia	Oceania
Communication Services	7.02%	8.68%	6.65%	9.09%
Consumer Discretionary	9.27%	11.03%	6.12%	10.71%
Consumer Staples	6.42%	9.58%	5.03%	11.43%
Energy	5.07%	6.71%	3.41%	2.73%
Financials	6.83%	8.05%	8.10%	15.32%
Health Care	9.46%	10.48%	4.53%	14.94%
Industrials	7.18%	8.46%	3.25%	11.04%
Information Technology	7.97%	9.06%	1.93%	10.00%
Materials	5.59%	7.49%	3.43%	6.69%
Real Estate	9.43%	7.71%	6.02%	15.49%
Utilities	16.03%	16.67%	6.17%	4.76%
Region Total	7.61%	9.07%	4.57%	9.36%

Color Legend: ≥12% (Dark Green) | 9–12% (Green) | 6–9% (Light Green) | 3–6% (Yellow) | < 3% (Red-Orange).

quota legislation has since been adopted in France (2011), Germany (2015), Italy (2012), Belgium (2011), Austria (2018), and the Netherlands (2022), with measurable effects on female board percentages in each country (Deloitte, 2023). Critically, Europe demonstrates that regulatory mandates can overcome cultural inertia: even countries with historically male-dominated corporate cultures have seen significant improvements following legislative action (Hamplová, Janeček, & Lefley, 2022).

Oceania's above-average performance, led by New Zealand (23.36%) and Australia (8.40%), reflects a combination of comply-or-explain governance frameworks, active institutional investor engagement, and cultural attitudes toward gender equality that are relatively progressive. The Australian ASX Corporate Governance Principles have included gender diversity reporting requirements since 2010, and major institutional investors, particularly superannuation funds, have exercised ownership influence to improve diversity outcomes (ASX Corporate Governance Council, 2023). New Zealand's exceptionally high figure (23.36%), while partly attributable to small sample size, likely also reflects both regulatory requirements and a cultural environment consistently ranked among the world's most gender-equal by the World Economic Forum (WEF, 2025). However, the effectiveness of comply-or-explain mechanisms depends critically on the rigor of enforcement and the transparency of explanations for non-compliance (Sojo, Wood, Wood, & Wheeler, 2016).

The Americas' proximity to the global mean despite the size and economic significance of the US markets reflects the limitations of a voluntary disclosure approach. While the SEC's 2020 amendments to Regulation S—K and Nasdaq's 2021 board diversity listing requirements created disclosure obligations, the absence of mandatory targets means that progress has been driven primarily by institutional investor pressure more than regulatory compulsion. Post and Byron's (2015) meta-analytic finding that the relationship between female board representation and financial performance is stronger in contexts with greater gender parity and shareholder protection rights suggests that the US voluntary model may be self-limiting: the governance benefits of diversity may not materialize fully until critical mass is achieved.

Asia's below-average performance, and Japan's position as the most extreme outlier in the sample, is consistent with literature documenting the structural barriers to female leadership in East Asian corporate environments (Dore, 2000; Inagami & Whittaker, 2005; Kambayashi, 2013). Japan's "womenomics" policy agenda, while politically prominent, has produced limited results in board representation because it has not been accompanied by meaningful regulatory enforcement or cultural change in corporate hiring, promotion, and career development practices. The present study suggests that without binding regulatory requirements, voluntary commitments and aspirational targets are insufficient to overcome deeply rooted institutional barriers.

The significant within-region variation documented in this study, particularly in Europe, where the range spans 18 percentage points from Austria to Portugal, has important implications for the corporate governance literature. This substantial disparity highlights that even within a single region subject to overarching regulatory frameworks, national contexts can produce markedly different outcomes in gender diversity on corporate boards. Such variation underscores the significance of country-specific factors, like legislative measures, cultural norms, and the strength of enforcement mechanisms, in shaping board composition. The European example demonstrates that regional trends may point toward increasing diversity, but progress remains uneven and contingent on the specific institutional and socio-political environments of individual countries. This finding suggests the need for future research and policy discussions to move beyond regional averages and address the nuanced factors driving intra-regional differences in corporate governance outcomes (Chen, Yan, & Yu, 2025).

Much of the existing comparative literature on board gender diversity relies on regional or block-level comparisons (e.g., Europe vs. North America), which can obscure the institutional heterogeneity that

exists within regions. The present study demonstrates that country-level institutional factors, including quota legislation, corporate governance codes, cultural attitudes, and educational pipeline characteristics, dominate regional patterns. The Austria finding (21.31%) is particularly noteworthy. Austria introduced mandatory board gender quotas for large state-owned enterprises and public limited companies in 2018, requiring 30% female representation. While the country's corporate governance culture has historically been conservative, the regulatory intervention generated measurable results even in the relatively short time since implementation. This is consistent with the broader European evidence that legislative mandates produce faster change than voluntary frameworks (Deloitte, 2023; MSCI, 2024).

Hong Kong's above-average performance in Asia (10.61%) warrants attention as a positive outlier. As a major financial center with significant international investor exposure and an active corporate governance reform agenda, including the HKEX's diversity initiatives under its Corporate Governance Code, Hong Kong demonstrates that Asian markets can achieve above-average female board representation when institutional conditions are conducive. The contrast with Japan (1.81%) within the same regional aggregate underscores that the Asia figure should not be read as representing a monolithic Asian corporate culture. Our results are in line with the figures presented in the Deloitte Global report on gender diversity on boards and women in leadership (Deloitte, 2023). According to Deloitte report, the percentages of board chairs that are women refer to: 8,6% in Nord America, 11% in Europe, 6,9% in Asia-Pacific, with 1,1% in Japan and 25% in New Zealand.

The sector-level findings are broadly consistent with prior literature but add nuance by providing a comprehensive cross-regional picture. The leadership of Utilities (13.20%) is consistent with the sector's regulated nature: public utilities operate under government oversight that creates incentives for governance compliance, including diversity. The sector also tends to have a more diversified professional workforce, with significant female representation in regulatory, legal, and administrative roles that feed the board pipeline (Deloitte, 2023).

Health Care's above-average performance (9.44%) is partly attributable to the feminization of the medical and pharmaceutical professions. As the proportion of women in medicine, nursing, pharmacy, and biomedical research has increased substantially over the past three decades, the pipeline of women qualified for healthcare executive and board roles has expanded correspondingly. This is consistent with resource dependence theory's prediction that board composition reflects the professional composition of the firms' external environment (Hillman et al., 2002; Berger, Kick, & Schaeck, 2014; Faccio, Marchica, & Mura, 2016).

The underperformance of Information Technology (6.33%) relative to both the global mean and to what might be expected given the sector's cultural associations with progressive values is among the most theoretically significant findings of the study. This paradox, documented in prior research (Blau & Kahn, 2017; McKinsey Global Institute, 2025), is typically explained by the pipeline problem: the gender gap in computer science, engineering, and mathematics education means that the pool of women with the technical credentials typically associated with IT leadership roles is disproportionately small. The board level reflects these constraints, with female directors in IT often coming from non-technical backgrounds such as finance, law, or marketing rather than from the technical executive pipeline.

Energy's position at the bottom of the sector ranking (4.92%) is consistent with the sector's history as one of the most male-dominated industries globally. Historically, the extractive industries had very low female workforce participation at all levels, and the board pipeline reflects these workforce demographics. Regulatory exposure is lower than in utilities, reducing the governance compliance incentive for diversity, and the cultural norms of the sector have historically been resistant to diversity initiatives (Deloitte, 2023).

Our analysis of disparity between the representation of women at the board and executive levels reveals a pronounced gap indicating that

progress achieved in increasing female participation on corporate boards was not mirrored at the executive level. While policy reforms and diversity initiatives improved board-level gender diversity in many regions and sectors, the advancement of women into executive leadership roles remains more limited. Thus, structural barriers continue to impede the development of a robust female executive pipeline, even as organizations strive to meet targets for board composition (Al Amosh, 2026). The persistence of this disparity highlights the need for integrated gender diversity strategies (Muhammad, 2025). Such strategies should not only focus on board appointments but also address the underlying institutional and organizational factors that affect hiring, promotion, and career development for women in executive positions (Kocanci, Aksoy, & Namal, 2025). Without comprehensive approaches that foster female leadership at all levels, board-level diversity may remain largely symbolic and fail to achieve the substantive influence associated with genuine gender equality (Gaspari & Giuliani, 2026).

Female executives constitute only 5.48% of positions, notably lower than the 7.23% female board rate. The statistical significance of this difference ($z = -6.285$, $p < 0.001$) underscores that the glass ceiling persists at multiple hierarchical levels within organizations. Moreover, female directors are more frequently appointed through external recruitment channels, such as academia, government, or other industries, rather than advancing through the internal corporate executive pipeline. This pattern aligns with established practices of appointing “token” female directors who enhance external credibility without addressing the underlying executive talent pipeline issues. Such appointments may improve the public image of gender diversity but effect no substantive change in internal leadership development (Acker, 2006; Kanter, 1987; Torchia et al., 2011).

The board-executive gap has important policy implications. If board-level diversity is primarily achieved through external recruitment rather than pipeline development, it may fail to address the underlying structural barriers to female leadership at the executive level. From a critical mass theory perspective, boards populated by externally recruited female directors who are not supported by a female executive pipeline may not achieve the substantive influence associated with genuine gender diversity, reinforcing the concern about symbolic versus substantive diversity (Torchia et al., 2011; Velte, 2025).

The methodological contribution of this study consists in the explicit attention to effect sizes alongside p -values. The Cramer's V values for regional and sector effects are both below the conventional threshold for a weak association, while all p -values are highly significant. This pattern, high statistical significance combined with small effect sizes, arises directly from the large sample size and reflects a common issue in large-sample social science research. The practical implication is that while regional and sector effects on board gender diversity are real and statistically robust, they are small in magnitude relative to the enormous common factor of global gender underrepresentation. A Utilities board in Asia has a female director rate of 6.17% above Asia's regional average of 4.57%, and reflecting the sector effect, but still significantly below gender parity and barely above the global mean of 7.23%. Policy interventions that rely on sector-level or region-level targeting will have limited impact unless accompanied by structural changes to the institutional environment, including mandatory quotas, pipeline development, and cultural transformation, that address the common factor of gender inequality.

How gender inequality is reproduced at the highest levels of economic power is one of the central questions in feminist scholarship on organizations, and the present findings speak directly to this question. Acker's (2006) concept of “gendered organizations” holds that ostensibly neutral organizational processes – job evaluation, hiring criteria, promotion decisions – systematically advantage men by encoding masculine norms as universal standards of competence and commitment. The data assembled here provide large-scale empirical support for this theoretical claim. The fact that women constitute only 7.23% of board directors across developed markets, and only 5.48% of executive

officers, despite decades of publicly stated commitments to gender equality, cannot be attributed to a simple shortage of qualified women. Rather, it reflects the operation of institutional filters – what Kanter (1976, 1987) called the “homosexual reproduction” of elites – through which those with selection power systematically favor candidates who resemble themselves in social background, educational pedigree, professional network, and, crucially, gender. The statistical pattern observed here – that underrepresentation is universal across regions and sectors, with Cramer's V below 0.10 in both the regional and sectoral analyses – is precisely the fingerprint of a structural phenomenon rather than a collection of idiosyncratic local biases. If exclusion were driven by specific cultural or industrial factors, we would expect the effect sizes to be large and the between-group variance to dominate. Instead, we find large between-region and between-sector differences in absolute terms, but a pervasive common factor of near-total male dominance that makes these differences appear modest by comparison.

The multi-layered character of this exclusion is further illuminated by the board-executive gap documented in Table 4. Women hold 7.23% of board seats but only 5.48% of executive officer positions ($z = -6.285$, $p < 0.001$), and this gap is itself theoretically significant. Agency theory, as applied to gender diversity by Adams and Ferreira (2009), predicts that female directors should improve board monitoring quality precisely because they bring different informational resources and behavioral tendencies to board deliberations. But this monitoring function is only fully effective when female directors are present in sufficient numbers and are themselves drawn from the senior executive pipeline, which provides the operational knowledge necessary to scrutinize management decisions with credibility. When female board directors are disproportionately recruited from outside the executive pipeline – from academia, public sector roles, or adjacent industries – as the tokenism literature suggests is common at low representation levels (Kanter, 1987; Torchia et al., 2011), their monitoring effectiveness may be constrained not by individual competence but by structural position. From a resource dependence standpoint (Pfeffer & Salancik, 2006), the pipeline gap implies that the networks and institutional relationships that female directors bring to the board are less likely to be embedded in the core industries where the firms operate, potentially limiting the strategic resources they can access on the firm's behalf. The compounding of exclusion across hierarchical levels is thus not merely an empirical curiosity; it is a mechanism through which the gendered architecture of corporate power reproduces itself across generations of leadership.

From the perspective of institutional theory, the sector-level findings also reveal important mechanisms through which gender inequality is reproduced at the intersection of occupational and organizational structures. The Energy sector's position at the bottom of the sector ranking (4.92% female directors) is not simply a reflection of individual recruitment preferences; it mirrors the historical feminization gap in the engineering and technical professions from which energy board directors are typically drawn (Blau & Kahn, 2017; McKinsey Global Institute, 2025). This pipeline effect is itself a product of gendered educational and vocational tracking that stretches back decades: women's underrepresentation in petroleum engineering, geoscience, and extractive industry management produces a compound exclusion at the board level that is self-perpetuating in the absence of active countervailing intervention. The Information Technology paradox is a further illustration of what Post et al. (2015) have called “decoupling,” in which firms adopt the discursive markers of diversity commitment while leaving the structural determinants of male dominance untouched. This pattern is consistent with DiMaggio and Powell's (1983) concept of normative isomorphism: firms in sectors with strong professional and cultural identities are subject to powerful mimetic pressures that reinforce incumbents' definitions of legitimate leadership, even when those definitions systematically disadvantage women. Conversely, the Utilities sector's leadership position (13.20%) reflects the normalizing effects of regulatory oversight: public utilities that operate under government supervision face governance compliance pressures that

explicitly include diversity, creating a coercive isomorphism (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983) that produces measurably different outcomes, though still well below parity. Critically, even the best-performing sector in the sample falls far short of the 30% critical mass threshold identified by Kanter (1976) and operationalized in recent meta-analyses of critical mass theory (Velte, 2025), meaning that the conditions for substantive, rather than merely symbolic, female influence over board deliberations have not been achieved in any sector in this sample. With a global female board director of 7.23%, the overwhelming majority of companies in the sample fall far below the 30% critical mass threshold, a finding that resonates across all four theoretical traditions and sharpens the urgency of the policy implications that follow. This integrated framework also connects the study to feminist institutionalism, which views organizations not as gender-neutral actors but as sites where gendered power relations are actively reproduced through ostensibly neutral procedures of recruitment, evaluation, and promotion (Acker, 2006). From this perspective, the underrepresentation of women on corporate boards is not a residual anomaly to be explained away but a constitutive feature of the gendered architecture of contemporary capitalism.

6. Conclusion

This study makes a substantial empirical contribution to women's studies by offering one of the most comprehensive cross-regional, multi-sector documentations of women's exclusion from corporate boardrooms currently available in the academic literature. Spanning 19,591 board director records across four regions, 35 countries, and 11 GICS sectors, the analysis provides the kind of large-scale, statistically robust evidence that feminist scholarship needs to challenge the structures maintaining male dominance in economic decision-making. The findings are unambiguous: women hold just 7.23% of board seats across the developed market companies examined here, a figure that is not merely a statistical observation but a measure of how far women remain from meaningful participation in the governance of global capital.

For women's studies, the significance of this finding extends beyond the numbers themselves. Corporate boards are sites where economic power is concentrated, strategic decisions are made, and the interests of capital are defined and defended. Women's near-absence from these spaces is not incidental, it is a structural feature of gendered capitalism that this study helps to map with precision and at a scale rarely achieved in prior research. By quantifying women's exclusion across regions, countries, and industries simultaneously, the study reveals the universality of the phenomenon while also exposing its geographic and sectoral variations, opening space for feminist inquiry into the specific institutional, cultural, and historical forces that produce different degrees of women's marginalization in different contexts.

Regional differences are statistically significant but modest in effect size, reflecting the universality of gender inequality rather than the concentration of the problem in specific geographies. Asia records the lowest female board rate, driven by Japan's exceptionally low 1.81% across the largest country sample in the dataset. Europe and Oceania perform above the global mean, attributable to regulatory mandates and institutional frameworks supportive of diversity; these two regions are statistically indistinguishable from each other, suggesting convergence. The Americas are statistically indistinguishable from the global mean. At the sector level, Utilities leads with 13.20% female directors and Energy lags at 4.92%, but all sectors remain far below gender parity. The region-sector interaction is highly significant, confirming that the gender diversity landscape is heterogeneous across the 44 region-sector combinations examined.

6.1. Implications for policy and practice

The findings of this study generate a set of clear, empirically grounded recommendations for policymakers, regulators, corporate boards, and institutional investors operating in developed markets.

At the regulatory level, the evidence strongly supports mandatory gender quotas over voluntary frameworks or comply-or-explain disclosure regimes. The comparison between European countries with hard quota legislation and those relying on soft mechanisms demonstrates that the direction and pace of change is decisively shaped by the binding character of regulatory intervention. For jurisdictions currently operating under voluntary frameworks, including the United States and Canada, these findings constitute empirical grounds for considering binding legislative mandates.

Regulatory targets must also be calibrated to the critical mass threshold rather than to incremental progress benchmarks. The data show that even the best-performing sectors remain well below the 30% threshold identified as necessary for substantive gender influence on board deliberations (Kanter, 1976; Torchia et al., 2011; Velte, 2025). Policy instruments that treat 20% or 25% female representation as a satisfactory endpoint are likely to institutionalize symbolic rather than substantive diversity. Policymakers should therefore adopt parity – defined as 40% female representation as a floor, consistent with the Norwegian model and the EU's Women on Boards Directive – as the operative target, and design escalating compliance timelines that prevent organizations from settling at tokenistic levels.

At the organizational level, the board-executive gap signals a critical priority: board-level diversity initiatives must be integrated with executive pipeline development programs to be effective. Organizations that appoint female directors through external channels without simultaneously building the internal executive pipeline are engaged in a form of governance optics that does not address the structural reproduction of male dominance. Practical recommendations at the organizational level include: structured sponsorship programs linking senior female executives with board-track mentors; transparent succession planning processes that explicitly track and support female executive candidates; job evaluation frameworks audited for gender-neutral criteria; and board composition reviews that assess not only the number of female directors but their committee memberships, independence classifications, and tenure distributions.

At the investor governance level, the findings highlight the potential role of institutional investors in driving change in jurisdictions where regulatory frameworks remain weak. The contrast between Hong Kong and Japan within the Asia region, and between Australia and other regional peers, suggests that markets with significant exposure to internationally oriented institutional investors – pension funds, sovereign wealth funds, and ESG-focused asset managers – achieve above-average female board representation even absent hard legislative mandates. Institutional investors operating in underperforming markets should consider developing and disclosing explicit gender diversity voting policies, engaging boards below critical mass thresholds through shareholder resolutions, and integrating board gender composition into their ESG scoring and stewardship frameworks.

6.2. Limitations and future research directions

The study has several limitations that future research should address. The cross-sectional design precludes causal inference or trend analysis; a longitudinal panel dataset would enable tracking of diversity improvements over time and assessment of policy intervention effects. The focus on developed markets leaves the emerging market landscape unexamined, where gender dynamics may be substantially different and where institutional frameworks for corporate governance are often in transition. The binary gender classification used in the dataset does not capture non-binary gender identities, a limitation with growing significance as gender diversity scholarship increasingly attends to the full spectrum of gender experience. Finally, the absence of firm-level performance, governance quality, and director biographical data precludes direct testing of the board diversity-performance relationship, analysis of director appointment pathways, or assessment of whether female directors are concentrated in particular board committees. Notwithstanding these

limitations, the study makes a substantial empirical contribution by documenting the scale and structure of gender inequality on corporate boards across a uniquely large and geographically diverse sample. The evidence leaves no room for complacency: at current rates of progress and without binding regulatory intervention, gender parity on corporate boards in the broad developed market universe remains a distant prospect.

Considering these limitations, some research directions are especially promising given the findings reported in the present study. The most important extension of this work would be a longitudinal panel dataset covering the same countries and sectors across multiple years, enabling difference-in-differences estimation of the effects of specific policy interventions such as quota legislation, governance code reforms, stock exchange listing rules on female board representation. The present data, collected in January 2026, establishes a baseline that a follow-up dataset in three to five years could use to assess whether the regulatory divergences documented here persist, narrow, or widen as the EU Women on Boards Directive and other recent legislative changes take effect. Longitudinal panel analysis would also enable tracking of the board-executive pipeline gap over time, testing whether organizational-level interventions translate into improved female executive representation with a lag.

Second, the focus on developed markets leaves a substantial part of global corporate governance unexamined. Extending the dataset to major emerging markets like Brazil, India, China, South Africa, Mexico, and Indonesia would enable comparative testing of whether the structural patterns documented here are specific to advanced capitalist economies or reflect a more universal feature of corporate governance. Emerging markets often combine rapid economic growth with institutional environments in transition, creating natural experiments in which the effects of newly adopted governance codes or cultural shifts toward gender equality can be observed in real time. The institutional theory prediction that regulatory and cultural factors mediate gender diversity outcomes could be rigorously tested across a much wider institutional range than developed markets alone can provide.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mihaela Herciu: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Claudia Ogorean:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Simona Vinerean:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Carolina Țîmbalari:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Data curation. **Alexandra Radu:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Radu Șerban:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

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